

A STUDY ON FACTORS INFLUENCING TOWARDS ONLINE SHOPPING IN TRICHY DISTRICT

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Abstract

These studies investigate factors influencing consumer's online shopping behaviour in Trichy district only. The further examinations of various factors influencing to purchase in online. In modern world shopping with Online is a new occurrence which was growing a great significance in the habitat. This paper analyzed the Factors influenced online shopping behaviour in Trichy district. The substantial numbers of online shopper dispense a great substratum for the expansion of online shopping. The consideration of online purchasing has unfastened the door of circumstances to utilize and furnish competitive benefits over firms. Respondents have been selected by convenient sampling for use Chi-square test and simple percentage analysis used to test the analysis. This paper motivation has to find out the factors influencing online shopping in Trichy district. Hypotheses are tested totally 100 samples are used.

Keywords: Online, Shopping, Factors, Influencing, Consumer, Behaviour, Purchase and Internet.

INTRODUCTION

Today online shopping are the main process for acquire products personally from a retailer without any intercessor, or it will be referred to as the activity of selling or buying goods beyond the website. Online shopping deal dispenses the consumer with the variation of products or services, where the customers can compare them with deals of other intercessors also select one of the best conventions for them¹. Till a many years ago, trading purely relied on offline stores to promote for sell their products and services. So many business corporations launched new branches in various localities in order to intensify their customer base². Online shopping is directly allowing the customer to buy the products and services from retailer over the online user in World Wide Web. Online shopping is a best and larger circumstance. Consumer number is increasing to buy the goods and services over the online shopping, congregate product details or even browse for enjoyment³.

The changing scenario peoples are sustenance in the virtual environment. Untimely, online has used as sharing the various information; there present day life is purely not possible without online. Moreover, the changing lifestyle of peoples has changing their way of doing things from offline to the new trend in which shopping is also being moved to shop internet. Everything are linked with the internet explorer, whether it is business, social relations of shopping. The number of customer's purchases online and the people spend most of time to

online have increased⁴. It has become most famous among customers to purchase online, as it is handier and save time⁵. Convenience, excitement and rapidity are the remarkable factors that have enhanced the consumer's enthusiasm in online shopping⁶. Moreover, busy situation and working long hours also make online shopping is accessible and saving the time solution over conventional purchasing of online. Customers have the comfort for easy payment of shopping from home, travelling time and cost has been reduced⁷.

Due to exponentially develop business excellent occasion, there are a numeral of amenity being provided for the website. Online shopping has materialized unanimously most important assistance available between online shopping. It has extensive superiority for the shopper as well as industrial unit. From end to end of online shopping, industrial unit have been able to connect with two more consumers at low cost. They had been able to connect with to buyer's sustenance in rural environment. In fact these are acting as stage of advancement to concept of virtual community. Although the stock management expenses also decrease significantly through online shopping⁸.

Objectives

1. To analyze factors influencing of online shopping.
2. To find importance of online shopping.
3. To study consumers online shopping behaviour.

Hypotheses:

1. H₁: Purchase online Consumers are satisfied.
2. H₂: Online purchasing the price is positively influence to purchasing.
3. H₃: There is a relation between consumer's behavior and perceived risk.
4. H₄: Consumer behaviour is a positive influence of trust factor.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Arjun Mittal (2013)⁹“this study is purely discuss the factors influenced from the online and examines those factors that influence the consumer behavior of online shopping. It starts with the present situation of the online evaluation, and mentioned the framework of marketing as representation and its difference with offline stores which in ordered to show the improving historical event of online shopping and E-commerce becomes the most popular. The main focus of this study is to obtain quantitative describing the actuality of online trading in the case of the India in order to explain the growth of online shopping”

R. mohammadabubakkar, Dr. M. Rifayameera, and R. padmaja (2017)¹¹“this study has been culminate that hereafter of e-tailors in India examinedazzlinge- tailors gives up the best method to save time and money through online purchasing with the range of budget. The success of any e- tailors organization in India is allocate its enthusiasm, its branding depiction

its distinctive and unbiased and its customers correspondence etc.,

Arya Prasad, Amal S U (2018)¹²“conducted a study based on online shopping department and initiate an alteration Input and output process representation. Online purchase group behaviors were also studied explain the significance of variety purchasing towards online trading. Major influenced factors that were found out from examination of this study are price, discrimination, quality, perspective, promotion, afford, options, accessibility, convenience etc”. These circumstances are classified to four category consumer perception, factors, website attribute and behaviour. There are inconsistent elements which stimulate the purchasing behavior of individual in the online programme.

Surajdebbarma and Sutapadebbarma (2018)¹³this study delegate with the advancement of online high technical, recent day online shopping becoming outstanding in recent propensity. Northeast India, which has obscure and is something cut off through the other states of India, online shopping is the expanding expeditiously and grow into market for e-selling. Therefore, understanding the factors that most influence the intention to use online purchasing among the people of northeastern region of India.

Sampling design and methodology

“The present study has an experimental research situated on analysis method. The research is confined of Trichy district. This paper is based on both primary and secondary data. Primary data composed through regularized Interview schedule from 100 respondents in Trichy district. The respondents for the study were depicted by means of simple random sampling method. SPSS collections were used for analysis. In order to find out the factors influencing online shopping behaviour in Trichy district”. Simple Percentage analysis and chi – square analysis has been used to discover any variances about consumer’s behaviour among the sample respondents.

Data Collection:

Primary Data:

The present study has used the both Primary and Secondary data. The pre-tested and well-structured interview questionnaire has used to collect Primary data.

Secondary Data

The required secondary data were collected from various Journals and Websites, magazines and articles.

Analysis: In achieve the objectives of the study an analysis is made to understand the consumer’s online shopping behaviour. The statistical tools used are percentage analysis and Chi-square test. The socio Economic profile of the respondent are shown in the following figures.

Percentage Analysis:

Table 1: Gender of the Respondents

The table 1 describes the gender wise classification of the respondent preferred for the study. The gender is classified as male and female.

Gender	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Male	56	56.0
Female	44	44.0
Total	100	100

Sources: Primary Data.

Table 1 is found from 56 (56 %) of the respondents are Male and 44 (44 %) are Females. It is concluded that the majority (56%) of respondents preferred for the study Male.

Table 2: Age of the Respondents

Table 2 describes the age of the respondents selected for the study. The age is classified as Below 25, 25-35, 35-45, 45-50 and above 50.

Age	Respondents	Percentage
Below 25	26	26.0
25 to 35	34	34.0
35 to 45	14	14.0
45 to 50	10	10.0
Above 50	16	16.0
Total	100	100

Sources: Primary Data.

It is clear evident from table 2 that 34 (34%) of the respondents belongs to 25 – 35 years, 26 (26%) of the respondents belongs to Below 25 years, 16 (16%) of the respondents are above 50 years, 14 (14%) of the respondents be held by 35 – 45 years and 10 (10%) are 45 – 50 years. It is concluded that the preponderance (34%) of respondents selected for the study are 25 – 35 age group.

Table 3: Education qualification

Table 3 describe the education qualification wise classification of the respondents selected for the study. The education qualification is classified as school level, under graduate, post graduate and Professionals.

Education qualification	Respondents	Percentage
School level	29	29.0
Under graduate	28	28.0
Post graduate	28	28.0
Professionals	15	15.0
Total	100	100

Sources: Primary Data

It is evident from table 3 shows that 29 (29%) respondent education qualification was school level, 28 (28%) of the respondents qualifications is at under graduate and Post graduate level, 15 (15 %) of the respondents belongs to up to Professional in their education. It's concluded that the most of the respondent (29%) preferred for the study are qualified at the school level.

Table 4: Occupation Statuses

Table 4 shows the occupation status of the respondents is select for the study. The occupation status is classified as employees, agricultural, business man, professionals, house wife and student.

Occupational status	Respondents	Percentage
Employees	32	32.0
Agricultural	04	04.0
Business man	16	16.0
Professionals	06	06.0
House wife	20	20.0
Student	22	22.0
Total	100	100

Sources: Primary Data.

It is result from Table 4 found the occupation status of the respondents. From the table it is clear that 32% of the respondents are employee out of the 100 sample respondents, 22 respondents (22.0%) are Student, 20 (20.0%) respondents are house wife, 16 (16.0%) respondents of them Business man, (6.0%) 6 respondents are professionals, (4.0%) 4 respondents belong to Agricultural category. Hence it may be concluded that a considerable number sample of 32 respondents (32%) are employees.

Table 5: What is your main Factor for using Online Shopping

Table 5 found that the respondent's main purpose selected for the study. It is classified into Shopping, Knowing product details, hobby and Time pass.

Products	Respondents	Percentage
Price	58	58.0
Trust and durability	24	24.0
Time convenience	10	10.0
Reputation	8	8.0
Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data.

Table 5 is indicate that the respondent main motivation to use online shopping. 58 respondents (58%) were stated that Price, 24 (24%) of the respondents are stated that Trust and Durability, 10 (10%) of the respondents are stated that Time convenience and remaining 8 respondents (8%) are mentioned Reputation. It is concluded that the majority of the 58 (58 %) of the respondents opinion that Price is main factor of online shopping.

Chi-Square Analysis

Table 6: Gender of the Respondents * which types of factors influenced in online?

		Factors influencing purchase online?					Total
		Price	Trust	Time convenience	Reputation	Experience	
Gender of the Respondents	Male	40	02	08	04	2	56
	Female	04	10	02	14	14	44
Total		44	12	10	18	16	100

Source: Computed for primary data. *Significance at 5% level.

Chi-Square Test

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson's Chi-Square	35.060 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratios	38.712	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Associations	13.750	1	.000
N of Valid Case	100		

a. 2 cells (20.0%) have expected less than 5 count. The minimum expected count is 3.60.

In the 6th table indicate that the chi-square value 35.060 with the degree of freedom 4 and the P value is 0.001. P value is less than 0.05, it can be inferred there is an associated between the genders of the respondents are which type of factors influenced of online shopping.

		What is your main purpose for using online shopping?				Total
		Shopping	Knowing product details	Hobby	Time pass	
Education qualification of the Respondents	School Level	17	4	4	4	29
	Under graduate	16	8	2	2	28
	Post graduate	17	7	3	1	28
	Professionals	8	5	1	1	15
Total		58	24	10	08	100

Source: Computed from primary data. *Significant at 5% level.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearsons Chi-Square	23.427 ^a	9	0.005
Likelihood Ratios	28.627	9	0.001
Linear-by-Linear Associations	2.718	1	0.099
N of Valid Cases	100		

a. 9 cells (56.2%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.68.

In the able 7, the chi-square test values are 23.427 with degree of freedom 9 and the p value is 0.005. Since the value of P is less than 0.05, it can conclude that there is dissociation between education qualification of the respondent and their main purpose for using online shopping is persuaded by education qualification of consumer.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

“Online as a new trend of purchasing is expeditiously developed for the India. This research helps to identify what are the factors are influenced in online shopping of Trichy. The Price is main factor and most influence the online purchasing. By online selling, an organization can Endeavour the cost reduction in a numeral ways and such frugality consideris passed on to the consumers in terms of Discounts. Besides offer and other selling informational techniques consider for undertakings to attract consumers to shopping the products through the online”. Behind the Price factor, convenience is another important factor that influences the online shopping. “Purchaser fined it much more suitable to shop at house and it also saving the time. Furthermore, customers look for conventional product details on the internet, a safety and fasten online remission system and cash –on- delivery facilities. Following the comfort, product is the next important factor that influencing the online purchasing of products”

CONCLUSION

“The research helps to determine the factors influencing of online shopping in Trichy district. Various components have been determined by consumers during online shopping. From the result, both the objective and subjective factors has been influenced to consume online shopping determination and behaviour. Therefore, while an online trader desire to be victory, people needs to acknowledge those components and contrivance the relevant scheme. While most of the online shopper thinking Cost (Price) is most influencing factor to buy online, consumers needed to encourage an applicable costing strategy to convince the require of consumer. Along with by setting a cheap price of the products, trader can also generate price benefits along with indirect price”. Six different elements came out for the analyze that restrict consumers to attachment from online shopping like selling Price, belief and durability, convenience of time, online shopping is more comfort for traditional shopping, acceptability & services provided and experience.

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